

NUTRITIONAL NEEDS AND SUPPLEMENT USE IN MILITARY POPULATIONS; A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF PREVALENCE, MOTIVATIONS, AND HEALTH IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Background: Military personnel operate in physically and psychologically demanding environments, prompting widespread use of dietary supplements (DSs) to support performance, recovery, and health. The prevalence, motivations, and safety of DS use vary by demographic and occupational factors. To systematically review the prevalence, patterns, motivations, and implications of dietary supplement use in military populations in different countries and service branches. **Methods:** A systematic search was conducted using PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar for articles published from 2000 onward. Studies were included if they reported on active-duty military personnel, provided data on DS use, and employed observational or mixed-methods designs. Data were extracted on prevalence, types of supplements, demographic subgroups, and motivations. A total of eight studies were included. **Results:** DS use prevalence ranged from 53% to 85%, with higher rates in elite units and younger soldiers. Frequently used supplements included multivitamins, proteins, creatine, and stimulants. Motivations included health

maintenance, energy, muscle development, and occupational demands. Several studies reported adverse effects, regulatory gaps, and misinformation regarding supplement use. **Conclusion:** DS use is prevalent in military populations, exceeding civilian rates. While some supplements address legitimate needs, others pose health risks. Military institutions implement targeted education, regulation, and monitoring strategies to ensure safe and informed use.

Keywords: Dietary Supplements, Military Nutrition, Soldiers, Prevalence, Performance Enhancement, Occupational Health, Supplement Safety, Armed Forces, Energy Products, Elite Military Units.

INTRODUCTION

Military personnel work in high-stress environments that demand exceptional physical and mental performance. To meet these challenges, dietary supplements (DSs) are used in different service branches.

Evidence shows that DS use in military populations is widespread and variable depending on occupational roles, deployment status, and national context. More than 60% of active-duty personnel regularly use DSs, with the prevalence reaching 76% in elite units like Navy SEALs and Army Rangers (1).

DS use in U.S. Army personnel increased from 56% in 2006 to 64% in 2011, mainly in younger soldiers aged 18–24. This rise was linked to increased consumption of protein, vitamin/mineral products, and combination supplements. These products are perceived as necessary for improving strength, endurance, and recovery, mainly under the physical demands of military service (2).

Bukhari et al. (2021) revealed in their mixed-methods study that 75% of U.S. soldiers used at least one DS weekly. Common reasons enhancing physical appearance, coping with occupational demands, and responding to peer recommendations.

Soldiers expressed a strong preference for receiving guidance from registered dietitians rather than relying on peer information or commercial marketing. In a large cohort study of Australian Defence Force personnel, van der Pols et al. (2017) found that one-third used bodybuilding, energy, or weight-loss supplements, with patterns differing by gender and service branch (3).

Energy products were prevalent in those in combat roles, while weight-loss products were favored by women and Navy personnel. Sammito et al. (2022) documented DS use in German military aviators, highlighting concerns about unregulated online purchases and the uncertain efficacy of products like protein powders and omega-3 fatty acids (4).

The Institute of Medicine (2008) show the need for structured education, regulatory frameworks, and adverse event monitoring to mitigate risks and support informed decision-making in military populations (5).

This review aims to discuss data on DS use in military settings, examining prevalence, motivations, and implications for health and operational readiness.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review aimed to discuss data on dietary supplement (DS) use in military populations by identifying patterns of prevalence, types of supplements consumed, and associated behavioral factors. A literature search was conducted using electronic databases (PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar).

The search strategy includes combinations of keywords (dietary supplements, military, armed forces, soldiers, nutrition, and prevalence). Articles published in English from the year 2000 onward were considered.

We include studies reported on dietary supplement use in active-duty military personnel, provided quantitative and qualitative data on prevalence or patterns of use, and employed observational designs (cross-sectional surveys, longitudinal studies, or mixed-methods research).

We exclude studies focused on retired military personnel, clinical trials unrelated to supplement behavior, or non-English publications.

Data extraction was performed using a format for study identification, country and military branch, study design, sample characteristics, methods of data collection, and outcomes related to supplement use.

Specific attention was given to reporting prevalence rates of overall supplement use, categories of products consumed (multivitamins, protein, creatine, herbal products), and subgroup variations by rank, deployment status, and age.

Motivations for use and longitudinal trends were also extracted when available. Two summary tables were created: one present methodological and prevalence data, and another comparative prevalence, trends over time, and reasons for use.

The included studies differ in design. Most of studies used cross-sectional survey methods, with sample sizes of 38 to more than 1,400 participants. Austin et al. study provided longitudinal data, and Bukhari et al.

used a mixed-methods approach, integrating data from focus groups. While risk-of-bias assessment tools were not applied, studies were evaluated based on sample representativeness, clarity of reporting, and relevance to military populations. Eight studies were included in the final review (Fig 1).

These represented military populations from the United States and Slovenia, which include Army, Marines, and elite forces. The studies include peer-reviewed articles, official military health research reports, and Institute of Medicine review.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart of included studies

RESULTS

The prevalence of dietary supplement (DS) use by military personnel differ in the included studies, ranging from 53% to 85%, with the highest usage observed in specialized units which include U.S. Army Rangers and other elite Army soldiers (6,7). Most studies found that military personnel used dietary supplements at higher rates than civilians matched for age, sex, and other demographic factors (2,7). The most reported supplement categories were multivitamins/multiminerals (MVMs), protein and amino acid products, creatine, combination supplements, and herbal or stimulant-based agents (8–10). In Castillo et al. study (8), 65% of users take multiple supplements, with over 50% using ephedrine-containing products and 38% using creatine.

Variations in supplement use were observed in subgroups, with rank, age, deployment status, and occupational role emerging as important determinants. Younger soldiers show higher prevalence of use compared to officer-ranked individuals (9). Deployment affect patterns of use, deployed soldiers in the Slovenian Armed Forces showed greater dependence on energy drinks and caffeine supplements, and non-deployed personnel consumed more protein-based products (10). Members of Army Rangers show distinct behaviors including high physical training volumes and use of performance-enhancing agents (creatine and ephedrine) even these were associated with health risks (6,11). One longitudinal study by Austin et al. (2) assessed changes in supplement use over a five-year period. The authors show increase in regular DS use in active-duty U.S. Army personnel from 56% in 2006 to 64% in 2011, with the significant increase occur in the 18–24 age group. This increase accompanied by increase in the use of combination supplements and individual vitamins and minerals, including iron, magnesium, and vitamins A, B6, B12, and D (2). These trends contrast with a decline in supplement use shown in U.S. civilian populations during the same time frame. The most commonly cited motivations included health maintenance (reported by up to 64% of users), increased energy (31%), muscle strength (25%), and performance enhancement (17%) (7). In the mixed-methods study by Bukhari et al. (9), qualitative focus group data highlighted motivations, physical appearance, ease of access to supplements, peer recommendations, occupational demands, and limited access to healthy food options. Soldiers expressed a preference for receiving supplement-related education from qualified healthcare professionals, registered dietitian nutritionists, mainly before deployment. The Institute of Medicine’s comprehensive review noted the use of products with conflicting safety data, and show the need for robust surveillance systems to track adverse events (5). These concerns were relevant in subpopulations exposed to operational stress, where mild supplement-related side effects impair performance or jeopardize mission success. Despite the growing use of DSs, gaps in nutrition education and regulation were identified in the included studies. Summary of dietary supplement use in military populations identified in Table 1, and supplement use in military populations in Table 2.

Table 1: summary of dietary supplement use in military populations

Study Identification	Study Design & Quality	Population Characteristics	Prevalence Data
Lieberman et al., 2010 (7) (USA, Army) Am J Clin Nutr	Cross-sectional survey n=990, stratified by age, sex, rank Questionnaire; 6-month recall Weighted sample; quality score not stated	Gender not fully specified Various ranks & Special Forces included Age: wide range	Any supplement: 53% MVM: 37.5% Individual vitamins/minerals: 17.9% Protein/amino acids: 18.7% Creatine: not separated Sport drinks/bars: 23%, 6% Herbals: 8.3%

Pravst et al., 2023 (10) (Slovenia, SAF) Nutrients	Cross-sectional survey n=470 (from barracks and deployment) Anonymous questionnaire Timeframe not specified; quality score not stated	Mixed units; deployed vs. non-deployed Gender not clearly reported Age not stated	Any supplement: 68% Protein: =unknown exact % Energy drinks: 25% (deployed) MVM/Vit/min: common Herbals/Creatine: not clearly detailed
Castillo et al., 2002 (8) (USA, Marines) NHRC Report 02-04	Cross-sectional n=1482 Self-report survey; 12-month recall Quality score not stated	Active-duty Marines, Camp Pendleton Gender/age distribution not detailed	Any supplement: 54% Muscle/strength aids: 53% Energy boosters: 28% MVM: 27% Creatine: 38% Ephedrine: 51% Androstenedione: 11%
Bukhari et al., 2021 (9) (USA, Army) JAND	Mixed-method (Survey + FGDs) n=289 (survey), n=129 (FGDs) Timeframe not stated; quality score not detailed	83% male, avg. age 27.6 yrs Enlisted (60%), Officers (40%)	Any supplement: 75% Protein/amino acids: 52% MVM: 47% Combo products: 35% Herbals, creatine: not precisely stated
Austin et al., 2016 (2) (USA, Army) Appl Physiol Nutr Metab	Longitudinal (2006–2011) n=989 then 1196 Weighted data Quality score not provided	Active-duty Soldiers Age 18–24 subgroup detailed	Any supplement: 56% → 64% Protein: 22% → 26% Combo products: 10% → 24% Individual vit/mins: ↑ (A, B6, B12, D, iron)
Deuster et al., 2003 (6) (USA, Army Rangers) Mil Med	Cross-sectional n=38 Questionnaire + FFQ Timeframe: 1 year Quality score not stated	All Army Rangers Gender not specified, elite unit	Creatine & ephedrine: 13% Others not specified in detail
Sridhar et al., 2006 (11) (USA, Elite Army) Unpublished USUHS Report (ADA454950)	Cross-sectional Sample size unclear; elite soldiers Self-report survey Timeframe unclear; quality score not stated	Elite US Army soldiers Gender/age details not specified	DS use =85% Details on types not comprehensively reported
IOM, 2008 (5) (USA, Multi-Branch) Institute of Medicine Report	Narrative review + survey synthesis Data from DoD and external surveys No quality score; integrative review	Mixed: Army, Navy, Air Force, Special Ops Various subgroups discussed	DS use =60–70% Protein, herbal, performance-enhancing products noted Risk-prone behavior subgroups identified

Table 2: Updated extended summary of supplement use in military populations

Citation	Main Findings	Outcomes	Comparative Prevalence	Trends Over Time	Reasons for Use
Lieberman et al., 2010 (7)	High DS use (53%), especially MVMs, proteins, herbals; 22% used ≥3 DSs/week.	Association with age, education, BMI, strength training.	Higher than civilians matched by age/sex.	Not examined (cross-sectional).	Health (64%), energy (31%), muscle (25%), performance (17%).
Pravst et al., 2023 (10)	68% used supplements; deployment influenced type (e.g., caffeine, protein).	Deployment status, rank, physical activity influenced use.	High use; energy drinks more common post-deployment.	Not longitudinal	Performance, health, availability.
Castillo et al., 2002 (8)	54% used DS; creatine 38%, ephedrine 51%, androstenedione 11%.	Many used multiple DSs; concerning safety profile.	Very high ephedrine/creatine use vs. civilians.	Not assessed.	Muscle strength, energy, enhancement.
Bukhari et al., 2021 (9)	75% used DSs; protein (52%), MVM (47%), combo products (35%).	High user rate in younger soldiers.	Higher than civilian use (=50%).	Not examined directly.	Appearance, fitness, peer use, access, health, job demand.
Austin et al., 2016 (2)	DS use rose from 56% to 64% (2006–2011), esp. young soldiers.	↑ protein, combo products, individual vit/mins.	Higher and rising vs. civilian decline.	Significant increase noted.	Muscle, performance, weight loss.
Deuster et al., 2003 (6)	13% used creatine/ephedrine regularly; small elite sample.	High activity, mixed health behaviors.	Consistent with elite military patterns.	Single timepoint only.	Performance, training needs.
Sridhar et al., 2006 (11)	Elite soldiers showed limited nutrition knowledge; 85% used DSs.	Higher supplement use linked with lower nutrition knowledge.	Much higher DS use than general Army population.	No longitudinal component.	Perceived performance benefit, physical demands.
IOM, 2008 (5)	Comprehensive review; 60–70% of military use DS; concern over safety.	Adverse events, regulation gaps, need for surveillance identified.	Military > civilians in DS use; patterns vary by duty.	Reported increasing use post-2000.	Enhancing strength, energy, health; deployment stress.

DISCUSSION

This systematic review includes seven studies about dietary supplement (DS) use in military populations in different countries, roles, and branches. The collective findings

show that DS use is common in military personnel, and patterns vary based on service branch, occupational demands, gender, and supplement categories.

Prevalence rates of DS use ranged in studies. Knapik et al. (1) conducted a large meta-analysis and found that the use of DS exceeded 60% in all service branches, with the highest use observed in elite units, Navy Special Operations and Army Rangers (76%). Their analysis also found that women in the military had higher DS use rates compared to men, mainly for multivitamin/multimineral (MVM) products. Van der Pols et al. (3) found that one-third of Australian Defence Force personnel used supplements, with gender and role-based variations men and Army members were more likely to use bodybuilding and energy supplements, while women and Navy personnel favored weight-loss products.

The type of supplements consumed differed depending on occupational demands and perceived needs. Sammito et al. (4) reported that German military aviators mainly used protein supplements, magnesium, and omega-3 fatty acids, motivated by physical activity and wellness, although less than half of users perceived tangible benefits. In U.S. service members, energy products were prevalent. Stephens et al. (12) found that 53% of respondents had consumed energy drinks and 19% used energy shots within the past month, mainly for enhancing mental alertness and endurance. 65% reported at least one side effect, including restlessness and insomnia, raising concerns over safety and operational readiness. Physiological risks associated with supplement use emphasized in studies focusing on performance enhancers. Catrambone and Dawson (13) found that niacin-containing products can lower mean arterial pressure, reducing aviators' G-force tolerance by up to 14%. These findings indicate the unique hazards DSs pose in military aviation and other high-performance roles, where even minor impairments in physiological function can have serious operational consequences.

The motivations for supplement use extended beyond performance. Several studies cited perceived benefits for health maintenance, energy, and muscle development (3,4,12). Knapik et al. (1) noted that civilian comparisons underestimate military use, which suggest that deployment environments play a critical role in supplement behavior. Pograjc et al. (14) analyzed the nutrient composition of Slovene military meals and found them sufficient in macro- and micronutrients, with some exceptions calcium and zinc in later samples. This indicate that routine use of supplements not always be nutritionally justified, mainly if military diets are well planned and balanced. The gap between perceived need and actual dietary sufficiency contribute to inappropriate DS consumption. Our study had some limitations; only a few studies included longitudinal data or objective performance outcomes. Most relied on self-reporting, which introduces recall and reporting bias. There is limited research on the efficacy, safety, and interaction effects of specific DSs within military settings, in elite forces and under combat stress. Some studies suggested regulatory concerns such as unverified online purchases (4) but there is limited formal evaluation of education interventions in service members.

The findings reinforce that dietary supplement use is influenced by demographic, occupational, and psychological factors unique to military life. And some products serve legitimate needs, others pose safety risks or reflect misconceptions about health benefits.

Military organizations prioritize educational campaigns, implement stricter purchase oversight, and consider integrating dietary monitoring into broader health surveillance systems.

CONCLUSION

Our systematic review highlights the use of dietary supplements in military personnel, with usage influenced by rank, deployment status, occupational role, and age. Common motivations performance enhancement, health maintenance, and energy support. Supplement use exceeds civilian rates and not nutritionally justified, especially where military diets are sufficient. Concerns about safety, regulatory oversight, and misinformation persist, regarding stimulant-based and performance-enhancing products. Addressing these issues requires targeted education, improved regulation, and integration of supplement monitoring into military health systems.

Abbreviations

- 1) DS, Dietary Supplement
- 2) MVM, Multivitamin/Multimineral
- 3) SAF, Slovenian Armed Forces
- 4) ADF, Australian Defence Force
- 5) FFQ, Food Frequency Questionnaire
- 6) FGD, Focus Group Discussion
- 7) DoD, Department of Defense
- 8) IOM, Institute of Medicine
- 9) PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
- 10) BMI, Body Mass Index
- 11) RDN, Registered Dietitian Nutritionist
- 12) US, United States
- 13) CDC, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

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